

Mechanism of Formation of β -Indolylpropionic Acid Derivatives

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A mechanism is proposed for the addition of 3-carbon compounds, viz., acrylic acid, acetamidoacrylic acid, etc., to the β -position of indole, resulting in 3-indolylpropionic acid, *N*-acetyltryptophan, and other similar β -indolyl compounds of biological interest.

The reaction is considered to be initiated by the addition of acetic acid to the acrylic acid moiety, followed by a base-catalysed elimination of acetate, leading to β -indolylpropionic acid derivatives. Divergences associated with other schemes have also been resolved.

Addition of acrylic acid derivatives to the 3-position of indole in presence of acetic acid and acetic anhydride was studied by several groups of workers^{1,2}.

Snyder and Macdonald¹ considered three possible structures (I-III) for the substrate arising of α -acetamidoacrylic acid to form *N*-acetyltryptophan by its condensation with indole and accepted none of them on the following grounds:

- (i) No acetyltryptophan could be isolated from the reactions in which indole was treated with a solution of 2-methyl-4-formal-5-oxazolone.
- (ii) Diacetylcysteine on treatment with indole yielded only a resinous product (uncharacterised) but no acetyltryptophan.
- (iii) 2-Phenyl-4-carboxyoxazoline, when treated with indole in presence of acetic acid and acetic anhydride, gave back only unchanged indole.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Johnson and Crosby² studied the formation of 3-indolylpropionic acid by an interaction of indole and acrylic acid in presence of a mixture of acetic anhydride and acetic acid. They suggested that acrylic acid during the reaction was converted by acetic anhydride to the corresponding mixed anhydride, losing thereby a molecule of acetic acid. The mixed anhydride on subsequent dissociation to the acryloid cation (IV) became the reactive species that added to the β -position of indole, resulting in 3-indolylpropionic acid.

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 1257.

2. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 25, 569.

The intermediate (VI) in the above reaction is such as to highly favour the formation of a 3-indolyl compound; there are ample chemical analogies⁴ to support this reaction involving a cyclic transition state.

The following observations lend further credence to the proposed course of the reaction:

- (i) Acetic acid is known⁵ to add to olefins and to acrolein.
- (ii) $\alpha\beta$ -Unsaturated nitriles, aldehydes, and ketones ordinarily add to 1,2-position, but the addition is 1,4- under the influence of basic catalysts⁶.
- (iii) ($\pm$)-Serine phosphate undergoes a similar reaction with indole in dioxane (solvent), resulting in tryptophan (vide Experimental).
- (iv) Whereas ($\pm$)-serine reacts with indole in presence of acetic anhydride to yield *N*-acetyltryptophan, *O,N*-dibenzoylserine under similar experimental condition is found unresponsive. Unchanged indole was recovered from the reaction mixture in almost quantitative yield. The addition reaction with serine undoubtedly involves prior formation of *O,N*-diacetylserine.

Snyder and Macdonald's failure¹ in isolating any tryptophan from the treatment of diacetylcysteine with indole neither proves nor disproves our scheme since the resinous product obtained from this reaction could not be characterised. Moreover, cysteine and its derivatives are known readily to polymerise under the influence of heat.

Johnson and Crosby² further pointed out that methyl acrylate, when used as a substitute for acrylic acid, failed to produce any indole-3-propionic acid. This observation is consistent with the sequence involving a transition state of the type(VI) and initiated by a pull of indolenine- β -hydrogen towards the carboxyl carbonyl of the free-acid moiety.

The above scheme of formation of 3-indolylpropionic acid has a further bearing on the genesis of tryptophan in nature. Earlier studies⁷⁻⁹ on the microbiological synthesis of tryptophan reveal that the final step in the formation of this compound involves a condensation of indole and serine (possibly through the phosphate ester) where pyridoxal phosphate is absolutely necessary as a co-factor. It has also been observed¹⁰ that during the condensation an intramolecular dehydration of serine (through the corresponding phosphate ester) takes place with the formation of α -aminoacrylic acid or a closely related compound, which forms the electrophilic substrate. All these findings can be accommodated in a scheme similar to the one considered above (Scheme A). The reaction is expected to involve a pyridoxal phosphate-aided Michael process, having a transition state of type (VII) and requiring two successive prototropic shifts *en route* to tryptophan.

4. Curtin and Kellom, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 6011.

5. Ballard and Geyer, *Chem. Abs.*, 1949, 43, 3026.

6. Kharasch and Tawney, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2308.

7. Davis, *Adv. Enzymol.*, 1955, 16, 247.

8. Doy, *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1960, 10, 185.

9. Demoss, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1962, 62, 279.

10. Harley-Mason, *Experientia*, 1954, 10, 134.

(VII)

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 3-Indolylpropionic Acid

(i). *In presence of Ac₂O-AcOH.*—To a solution of indole (2 g.) in acetic (2 ml) and acetic anhydride (2 ml) acrylic acid (3 g.) was added. The mixture was kept at the room temperature for 3 days. Solvent was removed from the reaction product under reduced pressure and the dark viscous residue left was basified with a 20% aqueous NaOH solution. Impurities were filtered, the filtrate acidified with HCl (conc.), and the precipitated crude 3-indolylpropionic acid (1.2 g.) crystallised from aqueous ethanol in pale brown needles, m.p. 133-34°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample remained undepressed.

(ii). *In presence of AcOH-AcONa.*—The above procedure was repeated with indole (2.1 g.) and acrylic acid (3 g.) in presence of acetic acid (4 ml) and sodium acetate (2 g.) when 3-indolylpropionic acid (1.3 g.), m.p. 124-28°, was obtained. A further crop (0.11 g.) was isolated on concentration of the aqueous acidic mother liquor at a reduced pressure.

(iii). *In presence of Ac₂O alone.*—Indole (1.2 g.) and acrylic acid (4 g.) in acetic anhydride (4 ml), when treated as usual, provided only unchanged indole. When indole (1.1 g.), acrylic acid (4 g.) and acetic anhydride (4 ml) were heated with stirring on a steam bath for 1 hr., the solution turned deep red. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the residue triturated with aqueous NaOH, impurities filtered, and the filtrate acidified. No 3-indolylpropionic acid precipitated even on saturating the solution with sodium chloride. The aqueous acid solution was extracted with ether, washed with water, and the extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent left a brown gummy residue (1 g.), which was crystallised from ether-light petroleum in colorless thin plates of indole, m.p. 52°.

(iv). *In presence of Acetic Acid alone.*—Experiment (i) was repeated with indole (1 g.) and acrylic acid (3 g.) in acetic acid (6 ml), when only unchanged indole (0.45 g.) was obtained.

Synthesis of N-Acetyltryptophan by Addition of (±)-Serine to Indole

(a). *In presence of Ac₂O.*—Acetic anhydride (5 ml) solution of a mixture of indole (1.8 g.) and serine (1 g.) was refluxed in an oil bath for 1 hr. and then left overnight. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure, residue cooled in ice, and water (2 ml) added

to it. The aqueous solution was diluted with ether (10 ml) to remove any unchanged indole. The aqueous fraction was basified with 20% aqueous NaOH. Acetyltryptophan (1.1 g.) was precipitated on keeping the mixture at the room temperature for a few hours. The brown solid was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless fine needles, m.p. 204-206°.

Hydrolysis of the *N*-acetyltryptophan with 10% NaOH and working up in the usual way furnished tryptophan, m.p. 272-76°. The compound was identified by its mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, which remained undepressed, and from the grey-blue colour developed in presence of ninhydrin reagent (ninhydrin dissolved in methanol to which collidine was added).

(b). *By Addition of Diacetylserine to Indole in Dioxane.*—Indole (1.2 g.) and diacetylserine (1.5 g.) in dioxane were treated according to the preceding experiment (a), when crude *N*-acetyltryptophan (1.1 g.) was obtained. The crude product was crystallised and subsequently hydrolysed with aqueous alkali to tryptophan.

Diacetylserine was prepared by dissolving serine (1.2 g.) in acetic anhydride (2 ml) in presence of pyridine (4 drops) and refluxing the mixture for 3 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the brown gummy residue left was used in the preceding experiment without further purification.

Treatment of Indole with O,N-Dibenzoylserine.—When indole (1 g.) was treated with *O,N*-dibenzoylserine (1.1 g.) similarly as above, only unchanged indole (0.7 g.) was obtained. The aqueous portion, expected to contain *N*-benzoyltryptophan, was hydrolysed with alkali and the hydrolysate indicated absence of any tryptophan, when treated with ninhydrin reagent.

O,N-Dibenzoylserine was prepared by dissolving serine (1.2 g.) in benzoyl chloride (1 ml) to which a 20% aqueous NaOH solution (20 ml) was added. The first 10 ml-portion of the alkali was added with alternate cooling and shaking. After the addition of alkali was complete, the flask was corked and vigorously shaken, when crude *O,N*-dibenzoylserine separated. The product was filtered, the residue washed successively with cold water and HCl (dil.), and crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 124°.

Synthesis of Tryptophan by Addition of (±)-Serine Phosphate to Indole in Dioxane.—A mixture of indole (0.75 g.) and (±)-serine phosphate (1 g.) in dry dioxane (15 ml) was kept at the room temperature for 4 days. The product was worked up as in (a), when crude tryptophan (0.5 g.) precipitated. It was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in flakes, m.p. 273-76° (decomp.).

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